

Letter of Intent AFRI NIFA Post-doctoral, November 7, 2011.

I. Applicant information:

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Mentor:

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II. Application information:

Post-doctoral research fellowship
Funding opportunity number: USDA-NIFA-AFRI-003538
Program area code: A7201

Project type: **Research**
Project Title: “Development of Functional Genomics Tools in Wheat”

Key words: wheat, food security, genomics, gene capture, induced allelic variants, plant immunity

Dear Agriculture and Food Research Initiative and the NIFA Fellowship committee:

I am writing this letter to express my intent to apply for the AFRI NIFA post-doctoral research fellowship. I obtained my PhD degree in Microbiology with Dr. Brian Staskawicz at University of California (UC) Berkeley in May 2011. Currently, I am employed as a postdoctoral researcher by Dr. Jorge Dubcovsky (UC Davis). The project I just started working on in the Dubcovsky's lab involves development of the genomics tools in wheat. Wheat is an extremely important agricultural crop, however, the genomic tools in wheat are currently lacking. I am proposing to develop functional reverse genetic tools in tetraploid wheat. The specific aims of my proposal include 1) characterization of wheat transcriptome, 2) development of exome capture and 3) assembly of a comprehensive mutant library, suitable for reverse genetics; in the final part of my project I will focus on characterization of functional mutants in wheat that control plant innate immunity. I have obtained extensive expertise in plant innate immunity during my PhD studies on *Arabidopsis*, and I am eager to transfer this knowledge to wheat. The results of the proposed study will have significant impact on providing means for engineering durable disease resistance in wheat, creating a diversity of allelic variants for agriculturally important traits and assisting basic research in wheat. My proposed research plan directly fits the goals of the AFRI foundation area - Plant Health and Production of Plant Products, and the AFRI Challenge area – Food Security.

I have dedicated my PhD studies to understanding the fundamental basics of plant innate immunity based on the plant model organism *Arabidopsis thaliana* and its native oomycete pathogen. In parallel, I gained a lot of bioinformatics expertise in computational biology, specifically, working with next-generation sequencing data. I believe that we need to study crop species with the same vigor as we apply to *Arabidopsis*, and the next generation sequencing techniques can provide the means to do it. I envision developing my career path in academia, and in ~three years starting my own group in wheat genomics and wheat molecular biology. I see my group having broad impacts: understanding wheat biology and wheat immunity against microorganisms will be transferred into development of resistant varieties. In turn, this will allow a greater food security for our growing population. As my mentor Jorge Dubcovsky holds a position of a Leader of the UC Davis Wheat Breeding Program, I will use my training years in his lab to better understand breeding programs. This will allow me to be aware of the specific breeding goals, and address them with my future research. Being a NIFA fellow will greatly help me to advance my career in science as an independent research leader. The NIFA fellowship will also provide me with funds to travel to national and international conferences and present my research. I believe that my achievements from PhD work, including three first author and co-first author papers, contributions to four additional publications, presentations at national and international meetings, and my passion for teaching make me a strong candidate for NIFA. I hope you will consider my application favorably.

If you have any questions about this letter or intended proposal, do not hesitate to contact me by e-mail: krasileva@ucdavis.edu or by phone: [REDACTED]

Sincerely,

Ksenia V Krasileva